

Assessment of the Viability of a 500 MW Concentrated Solar Power Plant in Gombe, Nigeria

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Executive Summary

The work assesses the viability of a 500 MW concentrated solar power plant project in Gombe, Nigeria. This is conducted by evaluating the impact of (i) electricity price, (ii) exchange rate, (iii) discount rate, and (iv) interest rate on the Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and shareholders' dividends, in assessing the power plant for possible viability. We found that the plant has a strong, positive correlation between price and profitability, with significant foreign exchange risk, where a weakening of the Naira will increase import costs more than it increases revenue. If the price drops by about 25%, the NPV turns negative, and the project becomes non-viable. At a baseline price of 250 NGN per unit, the project is found to be healthy, with an NPV of about 2.4 million NGN and an IRR of 18%. A higher discount rate will make the project appear less attractive today because of its negative NPV, yet it is financially viable and bankable, with clear sensitivity to interest rate changes. If market discount rates exceed 19%, the project is non-viable. The project will add value only if the cost of capital remains below a threshold of 19%.

Introduction

The world is undergoing a transition, as evidenced by the rising share of renewable energy (RE) sources such as wind, solar, and hydro. RE technologies accounted for over 14% of global power generation in 2022. Most RE resources are variable, limiting their ability to meet baseload energy needs. Due to the need for robust, cost-effective energy storage, concentrating solar power (CSP) is viewed as a promising renewable energy source for the coming decades. Concentrating solar power with thermal energy storage (TES) offers a major advantage over solar photovoltaics in terms of dispatchability (Calvert et al., 2024). CSP is a rapidly growing renewable energy technology; according to SolarPACES (2020), the global operational CSP capacity as of 2019 was

6.451 GW, up from 5.133 GW in 2017, a 20% increase. The associated cost of CSP has also been found to be declining over the years, with a target levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) for CSP baseload (≥ 12 h storage) plants reaching \$0.05 per kilowatt-hour by 2030 (Calvert et al., 2024). Nigeria is experiencing a continuously rising energy demand that far outweighs its supply, thereby consistently widening the demand/supply gap. The government of Nigeria, through the Electricity Act of 2023, has now unbundled all the segments of the power sector, i.e., generation, transmission and distribution. States and private individuals in Nigeria are now permitted by law to own power generation, transmission, and distribution facilities. The northern part of Nigeria falls within a high-sunshine belt, with attendant high irradiance and long sunshine duration. One of the states with very good irradiance, vast land and appropriate slopes suitable for RE projects, especially CSP, is Gombe. The plant will be sited in Gombe, Gombe State. The aim of this work is to assess the viability of a 500 MW concentrated solar power plant in Gombe State. Performance indicators, including NPV and IRR, will be used to assess the power plant's viability. This will be conducted by evaluating the variation of (i) electricity price on the selected performance indicators, (ii) exchange rate on the selected performance indicators, and (iii) discount rate and interest rate on the selected performance indicators.

2. Methodology

2.1 Site Selection

Gombe State (Figure 1) is one of the 36 states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, located in the centre of the north east of the country, on latitudes $9^{\circ}30'$ and $12^{\circ}30'N$, and longitudes $8^{\circ}5'$ and $11^{\circ}45'E$. It borders Borno, Yobe, Adamawa, Taraba, and Bauchi states, with a land area of 20,265 SQKM. The project is to be sited in Gombe in Gombe State.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing Gombe State (study site)

2.2 Methods

The Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN) model is adopted in this work. It is a global modeling tool for financial analysis of electricity, heat, water and CO₂ projects. The inputs to the FINPLAN tool were divided into four headings: cost-related data, technical data, economic and fiscal parameters, and financial data, while the outputs for each year are given as cash flows, balance sheet, financial ratios, NPV, IRR, etc. (Ilife, 2008; Vanhoutteghem, 1986; Nuryanti, 2016; Ishan bin Haji Bakar, 1989). Figure 2 shows the FINPLAN modeling tool.

Figure 2: FINPLAN Modeling Tool (Tsuanyo, 2024)

2.3 Data

The data utilized for the FINPLAN simulation are given in three segments, including technical, economic, and financial parameters.

2.3.1 Technical Information

This financial assessment covers the lifecycle of a 500 MW **concentrated solar power plant** facility from 2026 through 2051. Key project details include:

- a) Timeline: 4-year construction (2026–2029); 25-year operational life starting in 2026.
- b) Capital Cost: 2.5 billion USD and 2,250 billion Naira, distributed via a 4-year expenditure schedule (30%, 30%, 20%, 20% over the construction time) and depreciated over 25 years.
- c) Financing: Dual-currency [Naira (local currency) and US Dollars] using a blend of equity and debt.
- d) Revenue: 2,000 GWh annual production sold at an inflation-indexed rate starting at 0.34 Naira/kWh (\$0.09 USD).

- e) Operating Expenses: Combined O&M (\$28 million) plus a mandatory \$30 million decommissioning fund.

2.3.2 Economic Parameters

- a) Inflation USD: 2.7%
- b) Inflation Local Currency: 15.15%
- c) Exchange rate: 1500 Naira per USD for 2025 and 2026; the exchange rate reflects inflation rates
- d) Income tax: 25%, losses to be carried forward, no losses in start year.

2.3.3 Financial Parameters

- a) 70:30 Debt to equity ratio
- b) Cost of Debt: 12%
- c) Interest rate: 3% over inflation
- d) Equity: from 2026 to 2029, the following amounts in Naira are injected: 200, 500, 950, and 1125. No limit to dividends being paid out.
- e) Shareholders' targeted return data: 7% approx. average return, disposal year 2055 (in which the assets are assumed to be sold), discount rate: 15%

2.4 Sensitivity Analysis

This work investigates variations in: (i) electricity prices, (ii) exchange rate, (iii) discount rate, and (iv) interest rate. This financial analysis assesses the sensitivity of the selected parameters to key financial indicators, including Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and dividend, which are critical to determining the project's financial feasibility. This is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Sensitivity Analysis of Selected Financial Parameters

Sensitivity	Financial Parameters	Range of Variations	Indicators
1	Variation of electricity price	-35% ≤ Baseline (0%) ≤ 35%: Range of 5%	NPV, IRR, and Dividend
2	Variation of the exchange rate	1300 NGN ≤ Baseline (1500 NGN) ≤ 1750 NGN: Range of 50 NGN	NPV, IRR, and Dividend
3	Variation of the discount rate	Baseline (15%) ≤ 22%: Range of 1%	NPV, IRR, and Dividend

4	Variation of the interest rate	1% ≤ Baseline (3%) ≤ 5%: Range of 0.5%	NPV, IRR, and Dividend
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3.0 Results

3.1 Sensitivity 1: Variation of Electricity Price

Figure 3 shows the impact of the electricity price on the NPV and IRR. If the price drops by about 25%, the NPV turns negative, and the project becomes non-viable. The project is found to be healthy at a baseline price of 250 NGN per unit, with an NPV of about 2.4 million NGN and an IRR of 18%. It is also worth noting that IRR is not a straight line but a curve; hence, as the price increases, the rate of increase in the IRR slows gradually. Figure 4 measured the impact of electricity prices on shareholders' dividends. It can be seen that there are no dividends for the first 10 years of operation (2025-2034) in all the scenarios. At this period, the plant is likely in a phase of debt repayment or capital recovery, where cash flow is used to offset construction loans or to reinvest in operations before excess cash can later be shared among shareholders. Once the dividend payout begins, the rate is found to be exponential.

Figure 3: Variation of Electricity Price on NPV and IRR

Figure 4: Variation of Electricity Price on Shareholders' Dividends

3.2 Sensitivity 2: Variation of Exchange Rate

Figure 5 shows the impact of the exchange rate on the plant's NPV and IRR. The NPV and IRR fall steadily as the exchange rate increases. This indicates a significant currency mismatch: costs are denominated in a foreign currency (US Dollars), while revenues are denominated in the Nigerian Naira. At a baseline of 1500 NGN, the IRR is 19%. From Figure 5, if Naira weakens to 1750, the NPV drops sharply from 2.4 million NGN to about 1.4 million NGN, and the IRR falls below 18%. In Figure 6, the project's ability to clear debt will be compressed by using a higher exchange rate, thereby pushing the payout from 2036 (best exchange scenario) to 2042 (worst exchange scenario).

Figure 5: Variation of Exchange Rate on NPV and IRR

Figure 6: Variation of the Exchange Rate on Shareholders' Dividends

3.3 Sensitivity 3: Variation of Discount Rate

The impact of the discount rate on the NPV and IRR is shown in Figure 7. Figure 7 shows that increasing the discount rate reduces the NPV, while the IRR remains constant. Increasing the discount rate has no effect on the shareholders' return. If market discount rates exceed 19%, the project is non-viable; i.e., the project will add value only if the cost of capital remains below a threshold of 19%. From the discount rate impact on dividend (Figure 8), it is worth noting that the dividend paid out to shareholders is constant irrespective of the discount rate.

Figure 7: Variation of Discount Rate on NPV and IRR

Figure 8: Variation of the Discount Rate on Shareholders' Dividends

3.4 Sensitivity 4: Variation of Interest Rate

The variation in the interest rate on the NPV and IRR (Figure 9) shows that an increase in the interest rate reduces both the NPV and the IRR. The baseline is 3%, while the interest rate varies from 1% to 5% in increments of 0.5%. At the baseline, NPV is 2.4 million NGN while the IRR is 19.44%. Increasing the interest rate has almost no effect on shareholders' returns (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Variation of Interest Rate on NPV and IRR

Figure 10: Variation of the Interest Rate on Shareholders' Dividends

4.0 Discussion

This study measures the variations of (i) electricity prices, (ii) exchange rate, (iii) discount rate, and (iv) interest rate on the NPV, IRR and shareholders' dividend. It can be observed that there is a strong and positive correlation between price and profitability; hence, reducing electricity prices results in lower NPV and IRR. The NPV is very sensitive to price changes. The plant was found to have an appreciable buffer; if the price drops by approximately 22% i.e., from 250 NGN to 195 NGN per unit of electricity, the costs become optimized, and below this range, the plant will no longer be viable. The project also has significant foreign exchange risk; hence, a weakening of the Naira will increase import costs more than it increases revenue. We can further infer that a higher discount rate will make the project appear less attractive today because of the negative NPV; however, it does not reduce the cash being generated in the future; it only changes the value we place on the cash in the present. Lastly, the project is financially viable and bankable, with clear sensitivity to interest rate variation, but not fragile. NPV is more sensitive to interest rates, while IRR remains more stable, suggesting stronger cash flow.

4.1 Policy Recommendations

The following are selected policy recommendations:

4.1.1. The NPV and IRR are increasing with the rising selling price of electricity.

- a) **Reinvestment Policy.** If the price exceeds 200 NGN, the company should scale up by building additional capacity or acquiring similar assets. However, because of the stress on consumers with tariff increases, the government can set a threshold that works for both the developer and the consumer.

4.1.2. The NPV and IRR decrease as the exchange rate increases.

- a) Natural Hedging: Attempt to re-negotiate electricity sales contracts to be pegged to the foreign currency (e.g., a PPA priced in USD but paid in local currency).
- b) Localization: Shift the supply chain to local vendors to ensure that costs move in tandem with local revenue, thereby neutralizing the exchange rate's impact on the IRR.

4.1.3. An increase in the discount rate results in a reduction of the NPV while the IRR is constant.

- a) Monetary policy regulation: Targeted refinancing windows for infrastructure; Central-bank-supported green lending
- b) Local Currency Financing: Infrastructure bonds; Green bonds in local currency; Pension funds
- c) Hybrid Structures: Public–Private Partnerships (PPP)
- d) Tax Incentives: Tax holidays; Investment tax credits;
- e) Government Guarantees: Partial risk guarantees (PRG); Sovereign guarantees on offtake payments
- f) Blended Finance: Development banks (AfDB, World Bank etc.); Climate funds (GCF, CIF)

4.1.4. An increase in the interest rate results in a reduction of the NPV and IRR.

- a) Interest Rate Buy-Down / Subsidy Policy: The government pays part of the interest on project loans. This directly offsets the impact of high interest rates without changing tariffs.
- b) Credit Enhancement & Guarantee Policy: Partial risk or partial credit guarantees; Sovereign guarantees.
- c) Green or Strategic Infrastructure Lending Policy: Central-bank-supported lending windows; Preferential rates for power projects

5. Conclusion

This work measures the variations of (i) electricity prices, (ii) exchange rate, (iii) discount rate, and (iv) interest rate on the NPV, IRR and shareholders' dividend. The following were concluded:

1. There is a strong and positive correlation between price and profitability; hence, reducing electricity prices results in lower NPV and IRR.
2. The NPV and IRR fall steadily as the exchange rate increases.
3. Increasing the discount rate reduces the NPV, while the IRR remains constant, with no effect on the shareholders' return.
4. An increase in the interest rate reduces both the NPV and the IRR.

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